

THE LEGACY OF ANCESTORS IS THE ROLE OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE UPBRINGING IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY

PATRIOTISM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5006922>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th June 2021

Accepted: 15th June 2021

Online: 20th June 2021

KEY WORDS

military patriotism,
young generation,
culture, patriotic
education, tradition, civil
society.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the education of the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism through the legacy of ancestors, love and loyalty to the Motherland, the formation of moral and spiritual values and a sense of patriotism, orientation in everyday life to specific values of patriotism, religious tolerance, education of young people in the spirit of patriotism are considered as a general task.

Today, the upbringing of young people in the spirit of patriotism remains the focus of public policy not only in the educational system, but also in the penny of civil society.

Because patriotism is the basis of the viability of the state and serves as a source of internal mobilization for the development of society, the active civil position of the individual and his willingness to serve for the benefit of Vatan. Patriotism as a social phenomenon is an integral foundation for the emergence and development of the nation and statehood. One of the conditions for the stability of the state in this regard is the upbringing of young people in the spirit of patriotism. Patriotism, purposefully brought up in the younger generation, forms the moral and moral basis of the individual, its civil position and the need for worthy and selfless service to the motherland.

In the process of development of our republic today, for our state, which is on the path of building an independent legal and democratic society, the upbringing of a harmonious generation has increased to the level of priority policy. In the upbringing of the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism, it is important to realize the legacy of ancestors - their demonstrated courage and relying on our ancient traditions.

This was reflected in the speech of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at a solemn ceremony dedicated to the "may 9-day of memory and honor". In this speech, the head of our state, the Supreme Commander-in-chief of the Armed Forces said that "given the turbulent situation in the world and in the region, we must always live soberly and sensitively, increase the potential of our Armed Forces and educate our youth in the spirit of

patriotism and courage. The courage and glorious traditions of our great ancestors, distinguished veterans in the effective performance of such incredibly important tasks undoubtedly always serve as a lesson school for us. The high values and qualities of our people and nation are formed and developed on such a basis"¹ that emphasizes

It happened throughout our centuries-old history, our best fighting and labor traditions have not lost its rich spiritual strength. Its spiritual possibilities are much higher, and it has been appreciated so far.

Neck egmas Sogdiana and Bactria, Maraqanda and Khorazmshukh, people the courage of Shirak in the desert for his freedom (I century BC, Darius I) and the Companions of the spitamen mirror (324 – 327 BC years) A.Makedonsky, Abruy (VI century 80 - th year against Turkestan), Mukanna (VIII century 70-th year against the Arabs), Jalaliddin Manguberdi (1199-1231-th year against the Mongols), those who showed undeniable courage.

Amir Temur (1336 - 1405) and his descendants. Fitting (the founder of the great Mongols dynasty XV-XVI century) – all this national heritage, which has reached us from history our values, that is, our spiritual and educational wealth. Great the memory of such scholars as our ancestors Beruni (scientist 973 –1050y), Al - Khwarizmi (mathematician, geographer, historian 780 - 847y), Ibn Sino (Aviatsenna, medisina, asgronomy, geology 980 - 1037y), Imam Bukhari, Akhmad Yassavi, Ulugbek (School of asrology, statesman 1394 - 1449y) has

been a life - long and has occupied a positive place in the hearts of people.

On the fronts of the Second World War, the Uzbek fighters were great

they showed courage in a way worthy of the traditions of our ancestors.

For example, among them Sabir Rakhimov, Daniel Abdullaev, Bobohalil Kashanov, Ahmad Aliev, Nurum Siddikov, uzak Uthaeu and many other fighters defended our native homeland and showed heroism.

This is evidenced by the fact that more than 200 thousand of our soldiers and officers were awarded with combat orders and medals. 301 of our compatriots were awarded the title of hero of the Soviet Union, more than 70 were awarded the Order of Slava of three levels.

Heroic defense, giving a soul to their homeland on the battlefields did, we always keep in our memory that they have contributed with their hard work for the front inside the country.

According to the law of life, over time, many things are forgotten, forgotten. But in this lightdunya there is a sublime truth, it will never change, it will never become obsolete. That is," the memory of the people who showed courage and courage in the name of the happiness of Vatan and the people's freedom, the happiness of future generations, will always live in peace", insists the head of State.M. Mirziyoev.

Tradition is present, worthy of attention, passing from generation to generation social, economic attitude, connection with the socio - political system of society. The methods and methods of

¹ Speech by President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the day of memory and honor <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4335>

production, as well as the prevailing political consciousness, which are absorbed in the minds of people in a certain period and are constantly encountered in their lives, are developing day by day. In short, tradition is one of our national and Universal cadres inherited from the previous generation, which passed from one generation to the second generation.

The traditions of the Uzbek people to Uzbekistan, its land, its nature, love for their people, traditions, culture, history of our homeland striving to know. To be proud of the achievements and power of our Republic, etc. In the upbringing of young people, work is carried out based on the experiences of our generation and ancestors.

Traditions are determined by the exact historical basis of the people, taking them from one people by themselves can not be integrated into the second people. Every nation, a nation has its own traditions. Some of them may also have something in common.

For example: combat traditions are an expression from such labor traditions as the acquisition of military knowledge in the armies of many states, the love of one's own profession.

There are also such traditions, they belong only to this people, nationality or region.

In the Uzbek traditions and customs of the example, the people's heart and nature irreplaceable reflection: hospitality, hospitality, cocktails, respect for adults, childhood, love of nature and friendship.

Thanks to independence, all the values of our people have been restored restored. For this reason, the youth of the country they live in they must know their traditions and Customs.

Hospitality traditions are a common feature of society. This can be cited as an example of the assistance provided to families who were displaced from hostile lands during the Second World War.

Thousands of people found their peace here, for many, Uzbekistan has become a Vatan to them. In Uzbek families, children who lost their parents began to be brought up. On the square of the friendship of the peoples of the capital, a monument to the blacksmith Shamakhy Baba and his wife Bahri ayaga is erected. These patriotic people brought up children of 14 different nationalities and raised them in their bosom.

The traditions that arose and firmly established in society, first caused our society and the existing system. There is no doubt that in the primitive community system, its own traditions, unlike the present, were not the same in different peoples. They are people's culture, with its past, society it is connected with the social conditions in the relationship.

The power of ancestral heritage reflects, above all, the interests of Vatan and the service of Vatan defenders for patriotic education, the uniformity of the army and the people, the continuity of generations of citizens of a free, strong and independent country.

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